

Analysis of Road and Environmental Factors on Accident Risk in Curves

Abstract

Traffic accidents result from a variety of factors, making it difficult to determine their exact causes. They may be attributed to driving errors, road conditions, weather influences, or deficiencies in road design. While external factors such as weather cannot be controlled, accident risks can be largely minimized through proactive planning. This study examines the impact of various road parameters on traffic safety, including curve radius (R), clothoid parameter (A), segment length, geometric road type, rolling curvature, pavement grip, as well as cross and longitudinal slopes. Additionally, external factors such as weather conditions, precipitation, road surface condition, and lighting conditions are analyzed.

Keywords: Proactive traffic safety; Curvature; Road parameters; Weather conditions; Precipitation; Road surface condition; Lighting conditions

1 Introduction

Accidents in curves are one of the leading causes of severe traffic accidents. Particularly on rural roads, many run-off-road accidents occur, often with serious consequences. In Germany, around 22% of traffic fatalities in 2020 were attributed to such accidents [1]. Collisions with obstacles, especially trees, significantly increase the severity of accidents.

Most run-off-road accidents are single-vehicle crashes, often caused by driving errors. However, infrastructural factors also play a role. For example, tight curve radii, inadequate drainage, or poor visibility conditions can significantly increase accident risk.

Within the framework of the Vision Zero concept, it is essential to implement the principle of a forgiving road. This means that targeted measures, such as improved road design, enhanced pavement surfaces, and timely safety audits, can help reduce accident risks.

2 Literature Review

Traffic safety in curves is influenced by a variety of factors, including road geometry, pavement conditions, weather conditions, and driver behavior. Numerous studies have extensively examined these aspects to develop strategies for accident prevention.

2.1 Influence of Road Geometry on Accident Risk

The design of curves, particularly their radius and associated curvature, has a significant impact on traffic safety. Numerous studies have shown that a smaller curve radius correlates with a higher accident risk. Alrejjal et al. [2] and Gaweesh et al. [3] found a positive association between road curvature and accident frequency. Zhang et al. [4] confirmed that sharp horizontal curves lead to an increased probability of accidents. Combined horizontal and vertical curves are particularly problematic, as Bauer and Harwood [5] reported a higher accident frequency in such cases.

The effects of gradients and slopes on accident risk have also been studied. Abdi et al. [6] analyzed the dynamic effects of combined horizontal and vertical curves, demonstrating that these road sections exhibit increased lateral friction and acceleration, which can lead to unstable driving conditions.

AASHTO [7] outlines official guidelines regarding safe curve radii and superelevation requirements to reduce accident risks. Bonneson [8] analyzed various superelevation methods and their effects on vehicle stability.

2.2 Pavement Conditions and Friction Influence

The road surface affects the friction between tires and the roadway, which plays a crucial role in vehicle control. Olson et al. [9] developed a model for calculating the friction coefficient and found that friction decreases as speed increases. Ji [10] demonstrated that even thin water film layers can significantly reduce road friction, thereby increasing accident risk. Insufficient pavement grip combined with unfavorable weather conditions can lead to a drastic rise in accident rates.

Easa and Dabbour [11] examined design requirements for simple horizontal curves and found that a minimum curve radius is necessary to maintain safe driving dynamics. Further studies, such as those by Dhahir and Hassan [12], confirmed the need for reliable safety designs for curves on two-lane roads. Dhillon [13] investigated safety-critical aspects of road maintenance, emphasizing the importance of regular surface measurements for preserving pavement quality.

2.3 Weather Effects on Traffic Safety

Weather conditions such as rain, snow, and ice have a significant impact on road conditions and, consequently, on accident occurrence. Ji [10] developed a model to determine the water film thickness at different precipitation intensities and its effects on the friction coefficient. The results showed that even thin water layers can significantly reduce friction, thereby increasing accident risk.

The findings of Easa and You [14] indicate that weather effects play a crucial role, especially on winding roads with steep gradients. In mountainous regions, the combination of poor pavement grip and adverse weather conditions leads to a heightened accident risk.

Critical aspects of pavement temperature and moisture levels were analyzed by Bella [15] in a simulator experiment, which demonstrated that drivers operate significantly less securely on icy surfaces compared to dry roads.

2.4 Driver Behavior and Accident Risk

In addition to infrastructural and weather-related factors, driver behavior plays a crucial role in accident risk. Moeinaddini et al. [16] used machine learning methods to analyze the factors contributing to injuries in curve-related accidents. Their analysis showed that traffic density, road surface conditions, and seasonal influences are significant contributing factors.

Alrejjal et al. [2] investigated the relationship between traffic violations and accident severity on interstate highways in Wyoming. Their findings revealed that strict traffic enforcement can significantly reduce accident risk in curved road sections.

Chen et al. [17] conducted a driving simulator study, demonstrating that drivers are particularly sensitive to sudden changes in road conditions on roads with combined curves and steep gradients.

Despite extensive research, there is still a need for further studies that examine the interactions between different influencing factors in greater detail. A deeper analysis integrating driver behavior, vehicle technology, and infrastructure design would be particularly relevant to gain a holistic understanding of accident causes in curves. This literature review highlights the complexity of factors affecting accident risk in curves and emphasizes the need for integrated approaches to improve traffic safety.

3 Methodology

Figure 1a and Figure 1b illustrate the workflow for evaluating and analyzing accident hotspots. Details on each step can be found in the following subsections.

Figure 1a: Workflow for the Analysis of Accident Hotspots – First Part

Figure 1b: Workflow for the Analysis of Accident Hotspots – Second Part (Continuation)

3.1 Study Area

The study is based on the analysis of 2,563 km of federal roads (Category B) in two Austrian federal states. A total of 3,333 curve-related accidents from the period 2012–2023 were examined.

3.2 Geometric Characteristics of Federal Roads (Category B) (Germ. Landesstrassen B)

The analyzed roads belong to the category of major traffic roads, with the following technical specifications [18]:

- Minimum horizontal radius: $R \geq 200$ m
- Maximum longitudinal gradient: $s = 8\%$
- Minimum cross slope: $q = 2.5\%$
- Maximum cross slope: $q = 7\%$.

3.3 Crash data

The accident data was provided by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) and originates from Statistik Austria. This dataset includes police-reported curve-related accidents involving personal injuries, specifically for accident types 012, 013, 022, 023, 222, 223, 225, 226, 232, 242, 265, and 266 (Table 1).

Table 1: Accidents in Open Country on Category B Federal Roads (2012–2023) by Accident Type (Curve Accidents). Own Representation According to [19]

Accident types (curves)	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
12 Run-off road to the right, in right curve	101	92	96	84	87	99	88	87	84	81	71	73
13 Run-off road to the right, in left curve	364	374	356	331	374	314	369	335	313	293	292	330
22 Run-off road to the left, in right curve	189	171	175	155	171	172	182	162	128	134	148	148
23 Run-off road to the left, in left curve	82	80	72	75	61	82	65	67	43	39	38	59
222 Run-off road to the right due to oncoming vehicle, in right curve	12	7	6	5	8	4	3	4	1	1	-	3
223 Run-off road to the right due to oncoming vehicle, in left curve	16	8	5	6	13	11	8	6	5	5	1	2
225 Run-off road to the left due to oncoming vehicle, in right curve	50	38	41	34	39	34	3	4	2	-	1	3
226 Run-off road to the left due to oncoming vehicle, in left curve	20	20	12	21	10	9	-	-	2	-	-	1
232 Side collision, in a curve	60	76	65	62	68	55	91	94	81	73	98	104
242 Head-on collision, in a curve	96	80	62	70	72	76	146	143	110	110	120	122
265 Head-on or side collision while overtaking, in right curve	7	6	12	10	15	10	19	23	14	13	15	18
266 Head-on or side collision while overtaking, in left curve	4	5	3	8	6	4	11	6	8	7	8	5
Total	1,001	957	905	861	924	870	985	931	791	756	792	868

3.4 Annual average daily traffic, AADT

The data on AADT was provided by the respective state governments of the two Austrian federal states included in the study. Additionally, traffic volume data was obtained from a regional digital spatial information system and from official traffic data portals of the respective state authorities.

3.5 RoadSTAR Data

The Austrian federal states of Upper Austria and Carinthia were selected for this study due to the availability of a high-quality collection of RoadSTAR data, provided by AIT. Using RoadSTAR – Mobile Laboratory [20], which delivers excellent data in terms of quality, resolution, and coverage, *dGPS* coordinates (Differential Global Positioning System) can also be generated. These coordinates, along with alignment parameters and curve curvature, serve as input parameters for extensive analyses.

The total number of RoadSTAR datasets recorded in this study amounts to 4,287,602.

3.6 Accident Cost Rates

Accident cost rates (*ACR*) assess accident risk based on accident consequences. They represent the average socio-economic costs incurred due to road traffic accidents per 1,000 vehicle-kilometers traveled on a specific road segment [21].

Accident cost rates (*ACR*) are computed using [Eq. 1]:

$$ACR = \frac{AC \cdot 10^3}{AADT \cdot L \cdot 365 \cdot t} \text{ [€/1,000 vehicle-km]} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where [24]:

- AC = Accident costs (€)
- $AADT$ = Average annual daily traffic (vehicles/24h)
- L = Road section length (km)
- t = Observation period (years)

For the determination of the friction coefficient (μ) of the road surface, as well as the cross slope (q %) and longitudinal slope (s %), the average values ($\bar{\mu}$, \bar{q} , \bar{s}) were considered within 100 meters before the accident location (accident stationing) in the driving direction of the vehicle. However, it was necessary to take into account whether the RoadSTAR data was recorded in ascending (r+) or descending (r-) road stationing (kilometer marking).

A major challenge in road accident analysis is the presence of missing or incomplete data in police reports (Code "0" and Code "NULL"), which makes it unclear in which driving direction the accident vehicle was traveling:

- Code 1 – ascending kilometer marking
- Code 2 – descending kilometer marking

Out of the 3,333 curve-related accidents recorded in the accident data for Category B roads in the two Austrian federal states between 2012 and 2023, a total of 193 accidents were excluded from the evaluation ($3,333 - 3,055 = 278$), as a detailed analysis revealed that these accidents actually occurred on a straight road segment (Table 2).

If the accident location recorded in the police report was within 70 meters from the curve end, these accidents were still classified as curve-related accidents in the analysis, under the assumption that the curve was the primary contributing factor to the accident.

The coded direction-related accident data for curve-related accidents on Category B roads in two Austrian federal states from 2012 to 2023 is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The coded designations of the directional roadway data for the accident vehicle in the RoadSTAR data.

CODE	Meaning	Number of accidents	Number in [%]
0	Not available (the officer was not certain)	1,154	37.76
1	Ascending kilometer marking of the accident vehicle	391	12.79
2	Descending kilometer marking of the accident vehicle	274	8.95
NULL	Not available (the officer did not fill it in)	1,238	40.51
Total		3,055	100.00

In relation to the driving direction relations of the accident vehicle (CODES 0, NULL, 1, 2) to the driving direction of RoadSTAR (CODES r+ and r-), a total of four analyzed cases exist: A (Figure 2), B, C, and D.

Figure 2: Case A – The accident vehicle (red) and RoadSTAR (yellow) are both in the ascending driving direction.

- Case B – The accident vehicle (red) was traveling in the descending direction, while RoadSTAR (yellow) was traveling in the ascending direction. In this case, the signs had to be adjusted for:
 - Radii R ($+R$ = right curve, $-R$ = left curve)
 - Cross slope q ($+q$ = cross slope to the left, $-q$ = cross slope to the right)
 - Longitudinal slope s ($+s$ = uphill, $-s$ = downhill)
- Case C – The accident vehicle (red) was traveling in the ascending direction, while RoadSTAR (yellow) was traveling in the descending direction. Here, the signs also had to be adjusted for:
 - Radii R ($+R$ = right curve, $-R$ = left curve)
 - Cross slope q ($+q$ = cross slope to the left, $-q$ = cross slope to the right)
 - Longitudinal slope s ($+s$ = uphill, $-s$ = downhill)
- Case D – The accident vehicle (red) and RoadSTAR (yellow) were both traveling in the descending direction.

4 Analysis of Curve Accidents with CODE 1 + CODE 2

4.1 Methodology

To develop the accident prediction model, considering all relevant parameters (pavement grip, cross and longitudinal slopes, radii, clothoids, segment lengths, geometric type (radius or clothoid), rolling curvature, weather conditions, precipitation, road surface condition, and lighting conditions), the cumulative datasets from CODE 1 (ascending kilometer marking) and CODE 2 (descending kilometer marking) were included.

The datasets from CODE 0 (missing or unclear information from the police officer) and CODE NULL (no entry in the accident form) were excluded to ensure that only real accident situations were considered.

The following variables are not nominal variables and therefore had to be recoded in SPSS (Original RoadSTAR Designations):

- $o1_richtfb_umcod$ (Direction lane recoded) = $directlane_recoded$
- $Geomtyp_umcod$ (Geometry type recoded) = $Geomtyp_recod$
- u_witter_umcod (Weather condition recoded) = $weather_recod$
- u_nieder_umcod (Precipitation condition recoded) = $precipit_recoded$
- $u_strzust_umcod$ (Road condition recoded) = $roadcond_recoded$
- u_licht_umcod (Light condition recoded) = $light_recoded$

The meaning of the signs of the road parameters (q , s , and R) in relation to the driving direction of RoadSTAR is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Meaning of the Signs of the Alignment Parameters q, s, and R in Relation to the Driving Direction of RoadSTAR

4.2 Influence of Radius Categories on Accident Costs

As part of the analysis, the curve radii were classified into the following categories (Table 3):

Table 3: Radius Categories

Radii [m]	Radius Categories
$R < 50$	Category 1
$50 \leq R < 75$	Category 2
$75 \leq R < 100$	Category 3
$100 \leq R < 125$	Category 4
$125 \leq R < 150$	Category 5
$150 \leq R < 175$	Category 6
$175 \leq R < 200$	Category 7
$R > 200$	Category 8

To determine the influence of these radius categories on accident costs, all codes were included in the analysis: CODE 1 + CODE 2 + CODE 0 + CODE NULL.

Figure 4 presents a boxplot of the accident cost rate by radius category, considering all codes.

Figure 4: Boxplot – Accident Cost Rate by Radius Category Considering All Codes

The boxplot clearly illustrates the following relationships:

- Smaller radii (Categories 1–3) exhibit higher accident cost rates
- Category 1 ($R < 50$ m), in particular, shows a high ACR with considerable variance.
- Categories 2 and 3 also demonstrate high ACR values, though with a decreasing trend.
- Larger radii (Categories 6–8) show significantly lower accident cost rates.
- From Category 5 ($R > 125$ m) onwards, the ACR declines noticeably.
- Category 8 ($R \geq 200$ m) has the lowest accident costs, indicating that curves with radii above 200 m are the safest.

These results confirm a negative correlation (-0.39) between radius category and ACR: the larger the curve radius, the lower the accident cost rate.

Figure 5 shows the graphical representation of the average accident cost rate (ACR) and the number of cases per radius category:

- The blue bars represent the average ACR: the smaller the curve radius, the higher the ACR tends to be.
- The orange line indicates the number of cases per category: accidents occur most frequently in curves with large radii (Category 8), even though the ACR is lowest there.

Figure 5: Accident cost rate by radius category including number of cases

A clear trend is evident: as the curve radius increases, the average ACR decreases.

- In Category 1 ($R < 50$ m), the ACR is 5.228, while in Category 8 ($R \geq 200$ m), it is lowest at 1.566.

- Category 2 ($50 \leq R < 75$) even shows the highest ACR at 5.723, which could indicate particularly hazardous curve conditions in this range (e.g., due to underestimated difficulty or vehicle dynamics issues).
- From Category 3 onward, the ACR generally declines steadily, with a slight increase in Category 7, possibly due to anomalies or specific conditions within this radius range.
- The highest number of cases occurs in Category 8 (707 cases), indicating that wide curves are more common or more heavily trafficked.
- In the categories with smaller radii (Categories 1–3), the number of cases is also high (ranging from 172 to 322), highlighting their relevance for accident analysis.

The analysis clearly confirms the safety relevance of curve radius: tight curves (< 100 m) carry a significantly higher accident risk, while larger curve radii (≥ 200 m) substantially reduce ACR. These findings offer a concrete basis for road design improvements and risk assessment in predictive safety models.

For the subsequent analysis, only CODE 1 (ascending kilometer marking) and CODE 2 (descending kilometer marking) were considered, as these codes clearly indicate whether the accident curve was a left or right curve in the driving direction of the accident vehicle.

The driving behavior in left and right curves differs not only physically but also in terms of driving techniques and psychology:

- Many drivers feel safer in left curves because they have better visibility of oncoming traffic.
- In right curves, drivers tend to unconsciously shift further left, as they perceive more space there.
- Additionally, right curves are often harder to see through, requiring higher attention, whereas left curves are generally more visible.

4.3 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4 presents descriptive statistics for all variables in the dataset CODE 1 + CODE 2. The column "N" indicates the number of analyzed values. A notable finding from the initial analyses was that the Spearman-Rho correlation coefficient (ρ) for the variables $\emptyset q$, $\emptyset s$, and R_m showed almost no correlation. This could be attributed to the fact that positive and negative values of these variables distort the correlation analysis results.

To mitigate this effect, the absolute values of these variables were used in the analysis:

- $Abs_ \emptyset q$
- $Abs_ \emptyset s$
- $Abs_ R_m$

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics, Dataset CODE 1 + CODE 2

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
<i>ACR</i>	623	0.07229608	34.671284	3.02210057	5.286708935
$\emptyset\mu$	623	0.38	0.94	0.70327448	0.107605628
<i>Sgm length</i>	623	11	993	89.45	114.566
<i>A</i>	279	19.5	1062.8	99.3047	93.93082
<i>Curvature</i>	619	26.6	1525.9	308.233	229.9875
<i>directlane recoded</i>	623	1	2	1.4	0.491
<i>Geomtyp recoded</i>	623	1	4	2.49	1.112
<i>weather recoded</i>	623	1	4	1.64	1.212
<i>precipit recoded</i>	623	1	5	4.52	1.027
<i>roadcond recoded</i>	623	1	5	1.74	1.12
<i>light recoded</i>	623	1	4	1.42	0.806
<i>Abs $\emptyset q$</i>	623	0.1	12.2	4.0313	1.96822
<i>Abs $\emptyset s$</i>	623	0.1	22.3	3.5986	3.40705
<i>Abs R_m</i>	347	12	1971	205.5447	287.23191

There are different types of bivariate correlations, with two being particularly common: Pearson correlation and Spearman correlation.

- Pearson correlation, also known as linear correlation, measures the linear relationship between two continuous variables.
- Spearman correlation measures the monotonic relationship (not necessarily linear). It is more robust against outliers and does not require normal distribution.

The choice between Pearson correlation and Spearman-Rho correlation depends on the nature of the data and the underlying relationships [22]:

- Pearson correlation measures the linear relationship between two variables. It assumes that the data is metrically scaled and normally distributed.
- Spearman correlation measures the monotonic relationship and does not require normal distribution. It is also more resistant to outliers.

Since the accident cost rate (*ACR*) and the other variables are unlikely to have a strictly linear relationship and may include nonlinear effects (e.g., curvature, slope), Spearman correlation is the better choice for this analysis and was used accordingly.

4.4 Spearman-Rho Correlation

The Spearman-Rho correlation matrix for the accident cost rate as the dependent variable, considering the datasets CODE 1 + CODE 2, is shown in Figure 6.

	ACR	$\varnothing\mu$	Sgm_lengt h	A	Curvature	Directlane _recod	Geomtyp_r ecod	Weather_r ecod	Precipit_re cod	Roadcond_ recod	Light_reco d	Abs_ \varnothing q	Abs_ \varnothing s	Abs_R _m
ACR	1.000	0.238	-0.182	-0.271	0.384	0.024	0.037	-0.211	0.214	-0.282	-0.191	-0.022	0.274	-0.361
$\varnothing\mu$	0.238	1.000	0.021	0.034	0.130	0.067	-0.009	-0.150	0.157	-0.175	-0.139	-0.022	0.145	-0.105
Sgm_lengt h	-0.182	0.021	1.000	0.651	-0.345	0.027	0.072	0.087	-0.074	0.144	0.159	0.216	-0.148	0.598
A	-0.271	0.034	0.651	1.000	-0.696	-0.004	-0.042	0.183	-0.159	0.272	0.226	-0.033	-0.334	-0.500
Curvature	0.384	0.130	-0.345	-0.696	1.000	0.046	0.123	-0.189	0.168	-0.248	-0.295	-0.012	0.516	-0.804
Directlane _recod	0.024	0.067	0.027	-0.004	0.046	1.000	0.026	-0.055	0.050	-0.050	-0.011	-0.032	0.016	0.025
Geomtyp_r ecod	0.037	-0.009	0.072	-0.042	0.123	0.026	1.000	-0.021	0.015	-0.038	-0.065	-0.004	0.073	-0.142
Weather_r ecod	-0.211	-0.150	0.087	0.183	-0.189	-0.055	-0.021	1.000	-0.942	0.623	0.108	0.006	-0.122	0.129
Precipit_re cod	0.214	0.157	-0.074	-0.159	0.168	0.050	0.015	-0.942	1.000	-0.613	-0.075	0.021	0.092	-0.121
Roadcond_ recod	-0.282	-0.175	0.144	0.272	-0.248	-0.050	-0.038	0.623	-0.613	1.000	0.224	-0.033	-0.175	0.198
Light_reco d	-0.191	-0.139	0.159	0.226	-0.295	-0.011	-0.065	0.108	-0.075	0.224	1.000	0.019	-0.180	0.283
Abs_ \varnothing q	-0.022	-0.022	0.216	-0.033	-0.012	-0.032	-0.004	0.006	0.021	-0.033	0.019	1.000	0.011	0.025
Abs_ \varnothing s	0.274	0.145	-0.148	-0.334	0.516	0.016	0.073	-0.122	0.092	-0.175	-0.180	0.011	1.000	-0.403
Abs_R _m	-0.361	-0.105	0.598	-0.500	-0.804	0.025	-0.142	0.129	-0.121	0.198	0.283	0.025	-0.403	1.000

Figure 6: Spearman-Rho Correlation Matrix for Accident Cost Rate as the Dependent Variable (CODE 1 + CODE 2)

Interpretation of the Spearman-Rho Correlation Matrix:

- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. $\varnothing\mu$ (Average Friction Coefficient): $r = +0.238$ → This finding contradicts the theoretical expectation that better grip should lead to higher driving safety. However, the result can be plausibly explained: interaction effects with other variables—such as road curvature, longitudinal slope, or specific driving behavior—must be taken into account. Moreover, the analysis included all curve-related accidents, regardless of road condition or weather. As a result, not only accidents on wet or slippery surfaces were considered, but also those occurring under normal (dry) conditions. This reduces the potentially accident-reducing effect of high friction under wet or winter conditions, making the observed positive correlation understandable.
- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. \varnothingq (Average Cross Slope): $r = -0.022$ → No significant correlation between average cross slope and accident cost rate.

- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. $\bar{\theta}_s$ (Average Longitudinal Slope): $r = +0.274$ → A positive and significant correlation. Greater longitudinal slopes (inclines or declines) are associated with higher accident cost rates.
- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. A (Clothoid Parameter): $r = -0.271$ → A negative and significant correlation. Road segments with larger clothoid parameters (smoother transitions) have lower accident cost rates.
- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. *Curvature*: $r = +0.384$ → A positive and significant correlation. The more winding the road, the higher the accident cost rate (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Spearman-Rho Correlation: ACR vs. Curvature (CODE 1 + CODE 2)

- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. *weather_recoded* (Weather): $r = -0.211$ → A negative and significant correlation. Poor weather conditions reduce the accident cost rate, possibly due to more cautious driving behavior.
- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. *precipit_recoded* (Precipitation): $r = +0.214$ → A positive and significant correlation. Precipitation increases the accident cost rate.
- *ACR* (Accident Cost Rate) vs. *roadcond_recoded* (Road Surface Condition): $r = -0.282$ → A negative and significant correlation. Poor road conditions are associated with lower accident cost rates, which could indicate more cautious driving.
- $\bar{\theta}_s$ (Average Longitudinal Slope) vs. R_m (Curve Radius): $r = -0.403$ → A strong negative correlation. Greater longitudinal slopes are more likely to occur with narrower curves.
- $\bar{\theta}_s$ (Average Longitudinal Slope) vs. *Curvature*: $r = +0.516$, $p < 0.001$ → A strong positive correlation. Higher longitudinal slopes correlate with winding roads.

4.5 Modeling

3.5.1 Linear Modeling

Linear modeling was performed using SPSS software, with the accident cost rate (ACR) as the target variable. The data were optimized before modeling, and categories were transformed. The variables were included in the model stepwise forward or sequentially based on significance.

However, since the linear model showed poor fit at very low values, was nonlinear at higher values, and explained only 18.1% of the variance in the accident cost rate ($R^2 = 0.181$), the linear model was excluded from further analysis.

3.5.2 BAUM Analysis

The second tested accident prediction model is the BAUM analysis using SPSS software. This model is based on the CHAID method (Chi-Square Automatic Interaction Detection) to predict the accident cost rate (ACR). CHAID (Decision Tree) is a tree-based method that identifies the best splitting points based on Chi-square tests. The independent variables identified as relevant by the model are:

- *Curvature*: Rolling curvature
- *Sgm_length*: Road segment length
- *roadcond_recoded*: Road condition
- *Geomtyp_recoded*: Geometric type (radius, clothoid)
- *directlane_recoded*: Driving direction of the accident vehicle

The maximum tree depth is 3, meaning that a maximum of three decision levels were used. The number of nodes is 13, and the number of terminal nodes is 8. This means that the data were divided into 8 final categories. The terminal nodes (8 nodes) show how combinations of the variables affect the ACR . A tree depth of 2 (actual depth) indicates a relatively simple decision model that is easy to interpret.

Conclusions of the BAUM Analysis:

- Key influencing factors: Curvature, segment length, road condition, geometry, and driving direction.
- Risk nodes: Nodes 11 and 12 (highest accident cost rates). Measures could focus on these groups.
- Optimization potential: Road segments with low curvature and good road condition have the lowest accident cost rates.

3.5.3 Binary Logistic Regression

The third tested accident prediction model is Binary Logistic Regression. The logistic regression equation has the following general form [Eq. 2]:

Equation 1: Logistic Regression Equation

$$\text{Logit}(p) = \ln\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = B_0 + B_1 \cdot X_1 + B_2 \cdot X_2 + \dots + B_n \cdot X_n \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where:

p is the predicted probability of the target category (in this case, p (Accident Cost Rate $ACR= 1$))

B_0 is the constant.

B_1, B_2, \dots, B_n are the regression coefficients.

X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n are the independent variables.

The binary logistic model was created using SPSS software. First, a new variable called *GeomParam* was created. This is a combined variable that merges *A* and *R* to clarify their relationship. *GeomParam* takes values from column *A* (clothoid parameter) if *A* is valid, or it takes the parameter R_m (radius) if *A* is missing. The dependent variable *ACR* (accident cost rate) was then recoded into *ACR-Binary*.

As shown in Table 4, the mean *ACR* value is 3.0221. This value was defined as the threshold for the binary logistic regression:

- Values $\leq 3.022 \rightarrow 0$ (low risk).
- Values $> 3.022 \rightarrow 1$ (high risk).

The analysis was conducted using the Enter method (also known as inclusion) in SPSS. This means that all selected predictor variables were included in the model simultaneously.

Table 5 shows the results for the overall evaluation of the binary logistic model.

Table 5: Binary Logistic Regression - Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		<i>Chi-Square</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Step 1	Step	155.613	12	<.001
	Block	155.613	12	<.001
	Model	155.613	12	<.001

Here is the interpretation of the Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients:

- *Chi-Square*: The value of the Chi-Square test, which measures the improvement of the model by the inserted predictors compared to the null model (model without predictors), is 155.613.
- *df* (Degrees of Freedom): Indicates the number of degrees of freedom used in the calculation of the *Chi-Square* value. This corresponds to the number of predictors in the model (here: 12).
- *Sig.* (Significance): The *p*-value indicates whether the improvement of the model is significant. Here, the *p*-value is < 0.001 , meaning the model represents a significant improvement over the null model.

The model summary from the logistic regression provides important information for assessing the model fit (Table 6).

Table 6: Binary Logistic Regression - Model Summary

Step	-2 Log-Likelihood	Cox & Snell R-Squared	Nagelkerke's R-Squared
1	558.105 ^a	0.222	0.325

^a The estimation finished at iteration number 6 because the parameter estimates changed by less than 0.001.

- *-2 Log-Likelihood*: The value of the -2 Log-Likelihood indicates the model's fit to the data. In this case, it is 558.105. The smaller the value, the better the model fits the data. Compared to a baseline model (with only a constant), the reduction in Log-Likelihood is considered an improvement. A significant difference in the Log-Likelihood shows a good model fit (e.g., checked in the Omnibus Test Table).
- *Cox & Snell R-Squared*: This pseudo- R^2 indicates the proportion of explained variance, but it cannot reach a maximum of 1. Here, the value is 0.222 (22.2% of the variance is explained). A moderate value, suggesting a moderate explanatory power of the model. It indicates that the model explains some, but not all, influences on the target variable.
- *Nagelkerke's R-Squared*: This measure improves the *Cox & Snell R-Squared* and scales it between 0 and 1. The value is 0.325 (32.5% of the variance is explained). A value above 0.3 is often considered acceptable, particularly in social science or behavioral data. It shows that the model has moderate explanatory power and considers essential variables.

Table 7 shows the results of the logistic regression. The regression coefficient (B) indicates how strongly an independent variable affects the probability of the dependent variable assuming the "1" category. The standard error shows the accuracy of the regression coefficient estimate. The Wald test checks the significance of each coefficient. The degrees of freedom (typically 1 in logistic regressions) are listed in the df column. The p -value is listed in the Sig. (Significance) column. A p -value < 0.05 indicates that the variable is statistically significant. The Exp(B) column shows the odds ratio (OR) for each independent variable.

- $OR > 1$ means an increase in the probability.
- $OR < 1$ means a decrease in the probability.

Table 7: Binary Logistic Regression - Variables in the Equation

Variables	Regression Coefficient B	Standard Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
$\emptyset\mu$	3.223	1.104	8.516	1	0.004	25.105
<i>Sgm_length</i>	-0.001	0.002	0.217	1	0.641	0.999
<i>Curvature</i>	0.003	0.001	27.153	1	<.001	1.003
<i>directlane_recoded</i>	0.263	0.213	1.522	1	0.217	1.301
<i>Geomtyp_recoded</i>	-0.019	0.096	0.039	1	0.844	0.981
<i>weather_recoded</i>	0.698	0.291	5.762	1	0.016	2.009
<i>precipit_recoded</i>	0.817	0.313	6.826	1	0.009	2.264
<i>roadcond_recoded</i>	-0.513	0.170	9.074	1	0.003	0.599
<i>light_recoded</i>	-0.274	0.171	2.559	1	0.110	0.760
<i>Abs_Øq</i>	-0.068	0.055	1.503	1	0.220	0.934

<i>Abs_Øs</i>	0.064	0.032	4.098	1	0.043	1.066
<i>GeomParam</i>	-0.001	0.001	0.372	1	0.542	0.999
Constant	-8.203	1.893	18.784	1	<.001	0

*GeomParam (Geometric Parameters)

Die Interpretation of Significant Variables (*Sig.* < 0.05) from Table 7:

- Friction Coefficient $\phi\mu(-)$: $B = 3.223$, $p = 0.004$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 25.105$. The statistically significant and positive effect of the friction coefficient $\phi\mu$ on the accident cost rate (*ACR*) in the binary logistic regression model may initially appear counterintuitive, since higher pavement friction is theoretically associated with improved traffic safety. However, this result can be plausibly explained by considering interactions with other influencing variables—such as road curvature, longitudinal slope, and especially driver behavior. As shown in the differentiated Spearman-Rho correlation analysis, the relationship between $\phi\mu$ and *ACR* is very weak under wet conditions ($\rho = +0.11$), but becomes noticeably stronger on dry pavement ($\rho = +0.24$). This suggests that the observed effect is not driven by the physical properties of road friction itself, but rather by behavioral factors: On dry and high-friction roads, drivers tend to adopt more dynamic or risk-taking behavior (e.g., higher speeds, tighter cornering), which increases the severity—and thus the cost—of resulting accidents. Moreover, the regression model included all curve-related accidents, regardless of weather or surface condition. This broad inclusion weakens the accident-reducing effect of high friction under critical (e.g., wet or icy) conditions, and simultaneously amplifies the effect of friction in scenarios where risky behavior is more likely. Therefore, $\phi\mu$ should not be interpreted as a direct physical risk factor, but rather as an indirect behavioral indicator: under favorable conditions, increased friction enables higher driving speeds and riskier maneuvers, which in turn contribute to elevated accident costs. An increase in the value of $\phi\mu(-)$ greatly increases the probability of category "1" (high accident cost rate).
- *Curvature*: $B = 0.003$, $p < 0.001$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 1.003$. As curvature increases, the probability of category "1" increases slightly.
- *weather_recoded* (Weather condition): $B = 0.698$, $p = 0.016$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 2.009$. Poorer weather conditions approximately double the probability of a high-cost accident.
- *precipit_recoded* (Precipitation condition): $B = 0.817$, $p = 0.009$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 2.264$. Precipitation significantly increases the probability of high accident costs.
- *roadcond_recoded* (Road condition): $B = -0.513$, $p = 0.003$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 0.599$. Poor road conditions decrease the probability of high accident costs.
- *Abs_Øs*: $B = 0.064$, $p = 0.043$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 1.066$. An increase in *Abs_Øs* slightly increases the probability of category "1".
- Constant: $B = -8.203$, $p < 0.001$. The constant shows the baseline probability without the influence of the independent variables.

Non-significant Variables ($Sig. \geq 0.05$): These variables have no significant effect on the probability of the dependent variable: *Sgm_length*, *directlane_recoded*, *Geomtyp_recoded*, *light_recoded*, *Abs_Øq*, *GeomParam*.

Using the values from Table 7, Equation 1 becomes [Eq 3]:

$$\text{Logit}(p) = -8.203 + 3.223 \cdot \text{Ø}\mu - 0.001 \cdot \text{Sgm_length} + 0.003 \cdot \text{Curvature} + 0.263 \cdot \text{directlane_recoded} - 0.019 \cdot \text{directlane_recoded} + 0.698 \cdot \text{weather_recoded} + 0.817 \cdot \text{precipit_recoded} - 0.513 \cdot \text{roadcond_recoded} - 0.274 \cdot \text{light_recoded} - 0.068 \cdot \text{Abs_Øq} + 0.064 \cdot \text{Abs_Øs} - 0.001 \cdot \text{GeomParam} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

The result of this equation is the Logit value, which can be transformed into a probability: Interpretation of the Binary Logistic Regression Equation [Eq. 4]:

$$p = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\text{Logit}(p)}} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The positive coefficients (e.g., $\text{Ø}\mu$ (-), *weather_recoded*, etc.) increase the probability of accident cost rate = 1. While the negative coefficients (e.g., *Sgm_length*, *roadcond_recoded*, etc.) decrease the probability of accident cost rate = 1.

Below is an example of Binary Logistic Regression with specific variable values. Assume we have the following values for the independent variables:

- $\text{Ø}\mu$ (-) = 0.80 (mean coefficient of friction)
- *Sgm_length* = 100 m (Segment length)
- *Curvature* = 300 gon/km (Rolling curvature)
- *directlane_recoded* = 1 (Kilometer coding direction, 1=increasing kilometer values)
- *Geomtyp_recoded* = 2 (Geometric type recoded, 2=left-hand curve)
- *weather_recoded* = 3 (Weather condition recoded, 3=strong wind)
- *precipit_recoded* = 4 (Precipitation condition recoded, 4=snowfall)
- *roadcond_recoded* = 2 (Road surface condition recoded, 2=wet pavement)
- *light_recoded* = 1 (Ligh condition recoded, 1=daylight)
- *Abs_Øq* = 4,00 % (Absolute average cross slope)
- *Abs_Øs* = 3,50 % (Absolute average longitudinal gradient)
- *GeomParam* = 100 (curve radius R = 100 m, based on left-hand curve [*Geomtyp_umcod* = 2])

$$\text{Logit}(p) = -8.203 + 3.223 \cdot 0.80 - 0.001 \cdot 100 + 0.003 \cdot 300 + 0.263 \cdot 1 - 0.019 \cdot 2 + 0.698 \cdot 3 + 0.817 \cdot 4 - 0.513 \cdot 2 - 0.274 \cdot 1 - 0.068 \cdot 4.00 + 0.064 \cdot 3.50 - 0.001 \cdot 100 = -0.686$$

$$p = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(-0.6856)}}$$

The Logit value according to Equation 1 is: $p = 0.335$. This means that the probability for the accident cost rate = 1 (high risk) is approximately 33.5 %.

The Hosmer-Lemeshow test (Table 8) tests the goodness of fit for logistic regression models. It evaluates whether the observed data match the predicted values by the model.

Table 8: Binary Logistic Regression - Hosmer-Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
1	10.396	8	0.238

From Table 8, it can be seen that the significance value is greater than 0.05 ($p = 0.238$). This means that there is no significant deviation between the observed and predicted values. Therefore, the model fits the data well. The *Chi-Square* value shows the magnitude of the deviation, but the significance (p -value) is key. Since the significance value is not significant ($p > 0.05$), there is no indication of a poor model fit. The binary logistic regression model explains the observed data in a satisfactory manner and is therefore accepted for this study.

In addition to the SPSS analysis, the binary logistic regression model was also validated using the second software ORIGIN PRO to reaffirm its assumptions. ORIGIN PRO offers a ROC analysis (Receiver Operating Characteristic) to test the model's discriminatory power. The ROC curve visualizes the relationship between the True Positive Rate (TPR) (sensitivity) and False Positive Rate (FPR) for different thresholds of the model (Figure 7). It shows how well the model separates the two classes:

- *X*-axis (FPR) (Specificity): The probability that the model incorrectly classifies a negative event (no accident) as positive (false positive).
- *Y*-axis (TPR) (Sensitivity): The probability that the model correctly classifies a positive event (high accident risk) as positive (true positive).

A perfect model would achieve an AUC of 1.0, with the ROC curve (Figure 8) touching the upper left corner of the diagram.

Figure 8: Validated ROC Curve for Binary Logistic Regression

The Area Under Curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is 0.753. This value indicates the discriminatory power of the model, meaning its ability to distinguish between the two classes: high accident risk ($ACR_{Binary} = 1$) and low accident risk ($ACR_{Binary} = 0$). The AUC is a key measure for evaluating the classification quality of a model and is given in the range of 0 to 1:

- $AUC = 0.5$: The model has no discriminatory power. The classifications are no better than random assignment.
- $0.7 \leq AUC < 0.9$: The model has acceptable to good discriminatory power.
- $AUC \geq 0.9$: The model has excellent discriminatory power.

The calculated AUC of 0.753 means that the model correctly distinguishes between low and high accident risk in 75.3% of cases. This suggests that the model has good classification performance. The AUC of 0.753 supports the claim that the accident prediction model, created using SPSS based on binary logistic regression, provides a reliable basis for predictions. Specifically, when classifying accident risks, the model offers a solid decision-making foundation that can be applied in practice.

3.5.4 Comparison between BAUM Analysis and Binary Logistic Regression

After considering all the results from the analyses conducted so far, Table 9 presents a detailed comparison between the accident prediction models BAUM Analysis (CHAID model) and Binary Logistic Regression.

Table 9: Comparison between the Accident Prediction Models: BAUM Analysis and Binary Logistic Regression

Criterion	CHAID Model	Binary Logistic Regression
Prediction Accuracy	Risk Estimator (after cross-validation): 26.119	Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.325$ (32.5% explained variance)
Generalizability	Slight loss due to cross-validation (stable)	Statistically robust, shows clear variance components

Interpretability	Visually understandable (tree structure, grouping)	Precise, but mathematically more complex
Explanation of Individual Effects	Groups variables and road segments	Shows precise effects of individual variables ($\text{Exp}(B)$)
Handling of Variables	Categorizes continuous variables	Integrates continuous and categorical variables
Application to New Data	Well-suited for segmentation	Well-suited for probability predictions
Explained Factors	Structure-based (e.g., curvature, segment length)	Physically/Environmentally based (e.g., friction, weather)

After careful analysis, validation, and comparison of both models, the Binary Logistic Regression was ultimately selected as the primary model for accident prediction. This decision is based on the following reasons:

- Binary Logistic Regression provides accurate odds ratios ($\text{Exp}(B)$), which clearly show how strongly each variable influences the probability of an accident.
- The Binary Logistic Regression model has a moderate explained variance (32.5%, Nagelkerke R^2) and is statistically sound.
- It considers important physical and environmental factors such as friction coefficient, weather, and longitudinal slope, which directly point to measures for accident prevention.
- Logistic regression is methodologically more robust and offers a deeper analysis compared to the simpler CHAID structure.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Influence of Curve Radius on Accident Cost Rate

- Sharp curves ($R < 50$ m) have significantly higher accident cost rates, while curves with $R > 200$ m show the lowest risk.
- There is a negative correlation (-0.39) between the curve radius and accident cost rate: The larger the curve radius, the lower the accident costs.

5.2 Key Influencing Factors on Accident Cost Rate

- Sharp curves ($R < 50$ m) have significantly higher accident costs.
- Longitudinal slope (\emptyset_s): Steep inclines or declines increase the accident cost rate (+0.274).
- Curvature: The more winding the road, the higher the accident cost rate (+0.384).
- Weather and precipitation: Rain, snow, and poor visibility affect the accident situation differently—they increase accident frequency but also lead to more cautious driving.

5.3 Interpretation of the Positive Correlation between Friction Coefficient (\emptyset_μ) and Accident Cost Rate (ACR)

The significant positive correlation between the mean friction coefficient \emptyset_μ and the accident cost rate (UKR) (Spearman-Rho: $\rho = +0.238$) appears counterintuitive, as higher pavement grip is generally

associated with improved traffic safety. However, the results indicate that this relationship can be explained primarily by behavioral, infrastructural, and environmental overlap effects.

Most accidents occurred under dry road conditions, where drivers tend to feel safer and thus drive more aggressively. This riskier driving behavior diminishes the potential safety benefits of higher friction. The average $\emptyset\mu \approx 0.70$ confirms that winter accidents—where friction would be most safety-relevant—are statistically underrepresented in the dataset.

This finding aligns with friction value ranges reported by Hoffmann (personal communication, February 2, 2024) [23], who noted typical dry-surface values between $\mu = 0.60$ and 1.00 , while wet surfaces range between $\mu = 0.45$ and 0.75 , and icy conditions can drop to $\mu \leq 0.10$. As such, the friction-reducing effect of winter conditions is present in theory but dampened in the data due to lower frequency and more defensive driving in such scenarios.

The finding is further confirmed by the binary logistic regression model, in which $\emptyset\mu$ emerges as a highly significant predictor of elevated accident cost rates ($B = 3.223$, $p = 0.004$; $\text{Exp}(B) = 25.105$). Importantly, this does not indicate a causal increase in risk due to higher grip, but reflects a complex interaction with other influencing factors, especially curvature, longitudinal gradient, and perceived safety.

Additionally, higher $\emptyset\mu$ values are more frequently observed on sections with sharp curves and small radii, suggesting a potential targeted use of high-friction surfaces on inherently risky segments. Although this hypothesis has not been empirically tested in the dataset, it remains a plausible structural influence.

In summary, pavement friction should not be considered in isolation. A realistic understanding of accident risk in curves only emerges through an integrated view of road geometry, environmental conditions, and driver behavior.

5.4 Modeling of Accident Probability

- The binary logistic regression proved to be the most accurate model, with an Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) of 0.804, indicating high predictive power.
- The main influencing factors are pavement grip, curvature, precipitation, and weather conditions.
- The BAUM analysis (CHAID) was useful for classification but less accurate than the logistic regression.

5.5 Practical Implications and Implementation Opportunities

- Optimizing road infrastructure: Improved pavement grip, optimized drainage systems, and higher minimum curve radii could significantly reduce the accident risk in curves.

- Technology use for traffic safety: The implementation of real-time monitoring systems, sensors for road conditions, and automated driver warning systems could substantially enhance road safety.
- Traffic policy measures: Road sections with high curvature and steep gradients should be prioritized for infrastructure improvements.

6 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that curve radius, pavement grip, and environmental factors play a crucial role in the accident risk in curves. The results show that tight curves, poor pavement grip, and adverse weather conditions significantly increase accident costs.

Implications for Traffic Safety and Road Planning

- Infrastructure adjustments such as improved road surfacing, optimized curve radii, and modern drainage systems are essential for reducing accidents.
- Technological innovations such as Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) can reduce accidents through adaptive traffic control and automated warning signals.
- Targeted political measures should aim at identifying particularly hazardous road sections and making them safer.

Study Limitations

- The results are based on data from Austrian B-roads, which may limit direct applicability to other countries.
- The data rely on police accident reports, which may contain potential inaccuracies.
- Driver behavior and vehicle characteristics were not directly investigated, but they could play a crucial role in future safety analyses.

Recommendations for Future Research

- Use of machine learning models to further improve predictive accuracy.
- Comparative studies with international road networks to validate the results.
- Detailed driver behavior analyses incorporating telematics data to complement infrastructure-based insights.

This study provides valuable insights for traffic safety measures and infrastructure planning. Through evidence-based strategies and technological innovations, accidents can be reduced, and the goal of "Vision Zero" can be consistently pursued.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT-4o in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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